

Journal of Hazardous Materials
**Region-specific patterns of soil bacterial communities' adaptation to
Hexachlorocyclohexane contamination.**
--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	HAZMAT-D-25-25394R3
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	HCH degradation, lin pathway, lin independent pathway, Stenotrophomonas, Pseudomonas, Achromobacter, Pseudolabrys, Cupriavidus
Corresponding Author:	Simona Di Gregorio, PhD University of Pisa Department of Biology Pisa, ITALY
First Author:	Giacomo Bernabei
Order of Authors:	Giacomo Bernabei
	Devaki Destri, Dr
	Marta Franco-Benito
	Miguel Cebrian-Aldana
	Akanksha Mishra
	Sara Gil-Guerrero
	Jose Carlos Castilla-Alcantara
	Blanca Velasco-Arroyo
	Rocio Barros-Garcia
	Nicola Bertelloni
	Riccardo Di Mambro
	Simona Di Gregorio, PhD

Environmental implications

Our findings show that hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) degradation in historically contaminated soils extends beyond the canonical *lin* pathway. Robust HCH depletion in communities lacking a complete *lin* gene set reveals additional, still poorly resolved, but dominant microbial routes that can sustain natural attenuation at legacy lindane sites. The enrichment of multiple taxa in HCH-amended cultures points to several and new candidate degraders that could be tracked and selectively stimulated in bioremediation efforts. Together, these results underscore the importance of accounting for the broader functional potential of soil microbiomes when predicting HCH fate and designing management strategies for contaminated sites.

Soil Microbiome Adapt Beyond the *lin* Pathway: Microbial Degradation of HCH in Contaminated Sites

Highlights

- 64 bacterial consortia from DE, IT, ES were selected for HCH degradation capacity
- 16S functional inference suggested full *lin* pathway only in SP samples
- All enrichments efficiently depleted all HCH isomers despite differing *lin* pathway
- Suggested *lin*-independent pathway for non Sphingomonadaceae taxa
- Suggested HCH biodegradation by diverse taxa and *lin*-independent pathways
- Bioremediation options expand via *lin* independent HCH degradation capacity

Keywords

Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH), *lin* genes, *lin* pathway, *Stenotrophomonas*, *Pseudomonas*, *Achromobacter*, *Cupriavidus*, *Nocardioides*, *Pseudolabrys*, *Sphingobium*

1 Region-specific patterns of soil bacterial communities' adaptation to Hexachlorocyclohexane
2 contamination.
3
4
5
6
7 Giacomo Barnabei¹, Devaki Destri^{1,2}, Marta Franco-Benito³, Miguel Cebrian-Aldana³, Akanksha
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

¹Department of Biology, University of Pisa, Via Luca Ghini 13, 56123 Pisa. Italy

²BD Biodigressioni SRL, Lungarno Mediceo 40, 56127 Pisa, Italy

³Biotechnology Division, IDENER.AI, Aeropolis Parque Tecnológico Aeroespacial de Andalucía
N24 Unit 8, C. Earle Ovington, 41300, Sevilla

⁴International Research Centre in Critical Raw Materials for Advanced Industrial Technologies-
ICCRAM, Universidad de Burgos, Plaza Misael Bañuelos s/n, 09001, Burgos, Spain

⁵National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics, Via del Cedro 57122 Livorno, Italy

Corresponding author: Simona Di Gregorio – simona.digregorio@unipi.it

Abstract

Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) is a persistent organochlorine pollutant whose attenuation at former production sites relies on microbial degradation. The canonical *lin* pathway, predominantly associated with Sphingomonadaceae, is considered the main aerobic route for HCH transformation, yet its environmental distribution remains limited. We investigated soil bacterial communities and enrichment-derived bacterial consortia from three historically contaminated sites in Germany, Italy, and Spain using HCH depletion assays, 16S rDNA metabarcoding, and functional inference, based on a curated Anonymised dataset developed by “Anonymous” project. Based on the ASL-level

27 functional inference, the Spanish samples uniquely encoded a complete *lin* pathway restricted to
1
28 *Sphingobium* sp., whereas German and Italian communities harboured respectively partial (LinB–C)
3
29 or single-step (LinB) modules. Despite these differences, efficient depletion of all HCH isomers
4
6 occurred across all enrichment cultures. Core-microbiome and differential-abundance analyses
8
9 identified several non-Sphingomonadaceae taxa, including *Stenotrophomonas*, *Pseudomonas*,
10
11 *Achromobacter*, *Pseudolabrys*, and *Cupriavidus*, which consistently increased during selective
12
13 enrichment and likely contribute to HCH depletion. Overall, our findings suggest that effective HCH
14
15 degradation is not restricted to the canonical *lin* pathway nor to Sphingomonadaceae but it might be
16
17 mediated also by diverse soil bacteria via alternative *lin*-independent mechanisms. These results
18
19 broaden the known ecological and functional landscape of HCH biodegradation and support the
20
21 exploration of non-Sphingomonadaceae taxa for bioremediation of legacy lindane-contaminated
22
23 sites.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52

43 Introduction

44 Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) is a highly persistent and toxic organochlorine pesticide that was
45
46 historically used on a large scale in agriculture and public health, primarily as technical-grade HCH
47
48 (t-HCH) and its purified isomer, lindane (γ -HCH). Its extensive application has resulted in the
49
50 accumulation of large quantities of residues in soils and groundwater worldwide, leading to severe
51
52 and long-lasting contamination with significant ecological and human health risks^{1,2}. HCH isomers
53
54 are characterized by high hydrophobicity and chemical stability, properties that contribute to their
55
56 environmental persistence and bioaccumulation in food webs^{3,4}.

57
58 Microbial communities inhabiting contaminated soils can play a crucial role in the natural attenuation
59
60 of HCH through biodegradation. Aerobic lindane degradation is described as mediated by the *lin*
61

53 catabolic pathway, a series of enzymatic reactions that progressively dechlorinate lindane, converting
1
54 it into less toxic intermediates and ultimately mineralizing it to carbon dioxide and chloride ions ⁵⁻⁹.
3
4
55 The pathway comprises two major modules. The *upper pathway* module that includes LinA, a
6
56 dehydrochlorinase initiating dechlorination; LinB, a haloalkane dehalogenase catalyzing hydrolytic
8
57 dehalogenation of intermediates formed by LinA; and LinC, a dehydrogenase mediating subsequent
10
58 oxidation steps ^{10,11}. The *lower pathway* module completes mineralization of the chlorinated
13
59 intermediates generated upstream by LinA–LinC. Specifically, LinD (dehydrogenase) converts LinC
14
60 products into chlorophenolic species, which are hydroxylated by LinE and LinF to yield
18
61 chlorocatechols. These are subsequently cleaved and processed through LinG, LinH, LinI, and LinJ
20
62 (chlorocatechol 1,2-dioxygenase–associated reactions), generating open-chain acids. Finally, LinK,
22
63 LinL, LinM, and LinN catalyze reductive and rearrangement reactions that transform these
25
64 intermediates into central metabolites (e.g., succinate and acetyl-CoA), achieving complete
27
65 mineralization ^{7,12-15} Evidence for the involvement of the *lin* pathway in the degradation of all HCH
30
66 isomers, however, remains incomplete.
31
32
33
67 Several well-characterized HCH-degrading bacterial strains, such as *Sphingobium indicum* B90A,
35
68 *Sphingobium japonicum* UT26, *Sphingobium francense* Sp+, and *Novosphingobium lindaniclasticum*
37
69 LE124, carry *lin* genes and utilize this pathway ^{8,16,17}. These strains have been isolated from diverse
40
70 HCH-contaminated sites worldwide, underscoring the ecological relevance of the *lin* pathway in HCH
42
71 biodegradation. Even though the *lin* pathway has been reported within the family
43
72 Sphingomonadaceae ^{18,19}, several non-Sphingomonadaceae species have also been described as
47
73 capable of degrading HCH ¹⁹⁻²³, but the presence of the *lin* pathway in their genomes has not yet been
48
49
50
51
74 confirmed.^{19,24,25}
52
53
75 Given the central role of indigenous microbial communities in contaminant degradation and the
54
55
76 potential for HCH attenuation through biodegradation, this study investigated the microbial ecology
57
77 of three geographically distinct, historically contaminated t-HCH production sites located in Germany
59
78 (Bitterfeld), Italy (Colleferro), and Spain (Sabiñánigo) respectively. All three sites hosted
60
61
62
63
64
65

79 decommissioned production plants. The native bacterial populations potentially involved in HCH
1
80 degradation were identified and characterized by 16S rDNA metabarcoding. Subsequently, a
3
81 culturomics approach was adopted to recover and characterize bacterial consortia capable of HCH
4
6
82 degradation. To maximize the likelihood of isolating effective degraders, up to ten soil samples from
8
9
83 Germany, eleven from Spain and twelve from Italy were collected. An enrichment processes of HCH
10
11
84 depleting bacterial consortia in presence of high concentration of HCH and an additional carbon
13
14
85 source was adopted in parallel to the measurement of the kinetics of HCH depletion.
15
16
86 Initially, an investigation primarily aimed to identify bacterial taxa potentially harbouring the *lin*
18
19
87 pathway was performed and a predictive profiling was adopted. The predictive profiling was based
20
21
88 on the alignment of the bacterial consortia candidate proteomic sequences involved in HCH
22
23
89 degradation to a curated protein dataset specifically developed by the BIOSYSMO project²⁶.
25
26
90 This dataset provides a reference framework for mapping candidate proteomes and identifying which
27
28
91 functional steps of the *lin* pathway mediated HCH degradation are potentially encoded within each
30
31
92 soil samples and derived bacterial consortia. By combining taxonomic identification with available
32
33
93 genomic and proteomic information from the predicted candidate genomes, the approach allows
35
36
94 confirmation of *lin* pathway associated protein sequences intrinsically linked to the detected taxa,
37
38
95 contributing to a clearer taxonomic context for each soil area. Results obtained indicate that the Italian
40
41
96 bacterial consortia putatively encoded only LinB, indicating a hydrolytic single-step configuration.
42
43
97 German bacterial consortia putatively encoded LinB and LinC, supporting partial oxidative
44
45
98 capability, while Spanish bacterial consortia putatively retained the full LinA–F complement,
47
48
99 representing the complete *lin* pathway, suggesting a discrete functional architecture among sites. The
49
50
100 entire *lin* pathway was harboured only by the *Sphingobium* sp., whose presence was restricted to the
52
53
101 Spanish soil samples and derived bacterial consortia. The HCH degradative capacity of the different
54
55
102 bacterial consortia, even in the possible absence of the *lin* pathway, prompted a more detailed
57
58
103 investigation of the most effective bacterial consortia in terms of their degradation performance.
59
60
104 Three best performing bacterial consortia per site were selected for a comparative analysis of the core

105 bacterial consortia, shared with their corresponding contaminated soils. This approach enabled the
1
106 identification of taxa of potential relevance in HCH degradation, based on the assumption that taxa
3
107 present in the original soils and persisting through the HCH degrading bacterial consortia enrichment
4
6
108 process, particularly those increasing in abundance, represent strong candidates for HCH-degrading
8
109 capability. Results demonstrated that at genus level *Stenotrophomonas*, *Pseudomonas*, and
10
110 *Achromobacter*, increased significantly in abundance during the enrichment process of bacterial
13
111 consortia deriving from the German site (Bitterfeld, DE); in the case of the Spanish site (Sabiñánigo,
15
112 SP), *Sphingobium* and *Sphingomonas*, and of the Italian one (Colleferro, IT), *Pseudomonas*,
18
113 *Pseudolabrys*, and *Cupriavidus* spp. increased in abundance during the enrichment process.
20
114 Intermediates of degradation of HCH not referrable to the *lin* pathway have been identified. The
23
115 involvement of an efficient, non *lin* pathway dependent HCH degradation capacity in non
25
116 Sphingomonadaceae bacterial strains was proposed.
26
27
28

118 2. Materials and methods

119 2.1 Bacterial consortia enrichment and HCH depletion assays

120 Soil samples collected from the Germany, Bitterfeld (51°37'55.4"N 12°16'44.3"E), Italy, Colleferro
37
121 (41°44'37.4"N 12°58'56.8"E), and Spain, Sabiñánigo (42°29'03.7"N 0°21'17.0"W) regions at
39
40
122 dismissed industrial plants. The soil samples, deriving from historically contaminated sites, were used
42
123 as inocula in liquid culture, under selective medium conditions, to evaluate the degradation kinetics
44
45
124 of HCH isomers, while concurrently enriching bacterial consortia able to grow under the imposed
47
125 selective conditions. A total of 10 different soil samples were utilised from the German, 11 from the
49
50
126 Spanish site, 12 from the Italian one. The HCH depletion kinetics of depletion were used as the
52
127 criterion to select bacterial consortia with high degradation efficiency. A total of 576 sterile gas-tight
54
55
128 20-mL vials were prepared (6 vials per soil sample per time of analysis), each containing 5 mL of
56
57
129 Minimum Salt Medium (MSM) (KH₂PO₄, 170 mg; Na₂HPO₄, 980 mg; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 100 mg; MgSO₄,
59
130 4.87 mg; FeSO₄, 0.05 mg; CaCO₃, 0.2 mg; ZnSO₄, 0.08 mg; CuSO₄·5H₂O, 0.016 mg;
61
62
63
64
65

131 $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05 mg; MnSO_4 , 0.05 mg; H_3BO_3 , 0.006 mg) supplemented with HCH at a final
1
132 concentration of $100 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (α , β , γ , δ ; 1:1:1:1) and glucose at a final concentration of 0.1% w/v,
3
133 to facilitate potential co-metabolic processes during the degradation. In fact, these observations are
4
6
134 validated by the ones seen in previous studies, that have shown that co-metabolism between glucose
8
9
135 and HCH contributed to the capacities of soil microbial consortia to deplete all the HCH isomers ²⁷.
10
136 Two grams of previously homogenised soil sample were sieved under 2 mm. The sieved soil was
11
13
137 added to 30 mL of physiological solution (sterile deionized water with 0.9% w/v NaCl). The resulting
14
15
138 suspension was sonicated in a water-bath sonicator (Elmasonic P70H, Elma Schmidbauer GmbH,
16
18
139 Germany) at 37 kHz, 37 °C, and 100% power for 5 min 100 μL of the soils suspensions were added
20
21
140 to the 567 vials containing 5 mL of MSM with HCH and glucose (0.1% w/v) to achieve an inoculum
23
141 ratio of 2% v/v. As negative controls, three vials per time point were prepared containing MSM,
25
26
142 0.1% w/v glucose, and HCH at $100 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, without soil inoculum, and analysed at the
28
143 corresponding time points for residual HCH quantification. In addition, to confirm the absence of
30
31
144 possible biotic removal in control vials, 100 μL from each vials were plated on LB agar plates at the
32
33
145 time points of analysis to assess absence of microbial growth. LB is a complex (undefined) nutrient-
35
36
146 rich medium that supports the growth of a broad range of culturable bacteria. Even though not
37
38
147 exhaustive supported the absence of not specific microbial growth in the control vials. All the vials
40
41
148 (576 plus 9 control vials) were incubated at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the dark with orbital shaking at 130 rpm.
42
43
149 Six biological replicates were prepared for each sample and for each time point. Every 15 days, the
45
150 vials were opened and aerated under a sterile air flow ($0.8 \text{ NL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ for 10 s). Sampling times to
47
48
151 evaluate HCH depletion kinetics were at time zero, and after 30 and 60 days of incubation.
50

152 **2.2 Measurement of HCH depletion**

53

153 All soil samples used in this study were analysed by AGROLAB Italia S.r.l. (Via Retrone 29/31,
55
154 36077 Altavilla Vicentina, VI, Italy) to determine the concentrations of all HCH isomers, the certified
58
155 laboratory report result with a RSD% of 7-15%. Each liquid sample was analysed internally by GC-
60

156 FID. The vials, inoculated or not inoculated with soil samples, were extracted with an equal volume
1
157 of n-hexane containing $248 \mu\text{L} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ of fluorene as an internal standard. The mixture was vortex-
2
158 emulsified for 2 min, after which an aliquot of the non-aqueous phase was collected, treated by adding
3
4
5
6
159 0.1 g of anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , allowed to settle for 2 min in the dark at room temperature to remove
7
8
9
160 residual water, and analysed as follows: 1 μL of the extract was injected into an Agilent 7890B gas
10
11
161 chromatograph (GC) equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) and a 20 m column (0.18 mm
12
13
162 i.d., 0.18 μm film) coated with a non-polar stationary phase containing 5% diphenyl-polysiloxane
14
15
163 (HP-5MS, Agilent). Instrument settings were splitless injector mode, constant injector temperature
16
17
18
164 280 °C, septum purge flow $3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, inlet purge flow $40 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ after 1 min; isocratic
19
20
21
165 carrier gas (helium) flow $0.8 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. The oven temperature program was: 80 °C for 2 min; ramp
22
23
24
166 to 100 °C at $20^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, hold 1 min; ramp to 240 °C at $27.5^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, no hold; ramp to 250 °C
24
25
26
167 at $14^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, hold 4 min. The total run time was 14 min. Detector settings were: filament voltage
27
28
168 1.8 V, delay 240 s, mass range 35–500 m/z , and acquisition rate 12 Hz. Transfer line temperature
29
30
31
169 was 280 °C, source temperature 280 °C, and ionization potential -70 eV . Each extract was injected
32
33
170 twice into the GC-FID, yielding three biological and three technical replicates per sample analyzed.
34
35
36
171 For GC-FID calibration, dilutions were prepared from an HCH stock solution at $0.46 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (α , β , γ ,
37
38
172 δ ; 1:1:1:1; Sigma-Aldrich) dissolved in acetone. A calibration curve was generated by interpolating
39
40
41
173 signals from five serial dilutions spanning 0–100 $\text{mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ per isomer. Calibration curves were fitted
42
43
44
174 with a free intercept; an instrument blank containing hexane only was used to detect possible
45
46
175 contamination. The R^2 values for the α -, β -, γ -, and δ -isomers were 0.999, 0.995, 0.986, and 0.999,
47
48
49
176 respectively. From a fluorene stock solution at $1.02 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in hexane, a spike was added to the
50
51
177 extraction solvent to obtain a final concentration of $248 \mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ fluorene in each sample, used as the
52
53
178 internal standard. Chromatographic peak integration was performed by normalizing the baseline-
54
55
179 integrated area of each analyte peak to the chromatographic peak area of the internal standard, thereby
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

180 yielding four normalized areas, one for each isomer analysed. Post hoc comparisons use Dunn's test
1
181 with Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple comparison (nparLD v2.2, rstatix v0.7.2) ²⁸.

182

183 **2.3 Identification of HCH metabolites of degradation**

184 The identification of HCH metabolites of the degradation process by the different bacterial consortia
11
185 was attempted by chromatographic analyses using an Agilent 7890B GC system (Agilent
14
186 Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with a Bench-TOF time-of-flight mass analyzer
16
187 (Markes International Ltd., Llantrisant, United Kingdom). Helium was used as the carrier gas.
19
188 Injections were carried out in split mode: a split ratio of 1:20 was used for the quantification of
21
189 analytes, while a split ratio of 1:2 was employed for the detection of metabolites. The installed
24
190 capillary column was a DB-5MS (30 m × 0.25 mm i.d. × 0.25 µm film thickness) provided by Agilent
26
191 Technologies. The temperature program was as follows: the initial temperature of 80 °C was held for
28
192 1 minute, then increased to 280 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. The Bench-TOF ionization source was set
31
193 to -70 eV, and the transfer line temperature was maintained at 250 °C ^{29–31} Data acquisition was
33
194 performed in Total Ion Current (TIC) mode to obtain a full scan of the ions generated during
36
195 fragmentation. Metabolite identification was carried out using ChromSpace software dedicated to the
38
196 integrated management of chromatographic and mass spectrometry data. Each significant signal
41
197 detected in the chromatogram was analyzed by means of the mass spectrum associated with the
43
198 corresponding peak and compared against the EPA-NIST-NIH spectral library installed in the system,
46
199 based on the percentage of spectral overlap (match). Each spectrum was additionally subjected to
48
200 manual verification, the expected fragmentation patterns were evaluated using, as the primary
50
201 discriminating criterion, the presence of the characteristic isotopic pattern of chlorine: an element
53
202 naturally occurring as ³⁵Cl (76%) and ³⁷Cl (24%), which generates characteristic signals in the mass
55
203 spectrum (e.g., [M]⁺, [M+2]⁺, and [M+4]⁺), thus representing a distinctive marker for the recognition
58
204 of chlorinated compounds and their transformation products. In relation to the extraction procedure,
60

205 each sample was taken from the freezer ($-21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and left to thaw at room temperature. A solution of
1
206 fluorene in acetone was prepared at a concentration of 1000 ppm, and each sample was spiked with
3
207 fluorene at 100 ppm; samples were then vortexed for 1 minute to ensure homogeneity. A dispersive
4
6
208 liquid-liquid extraction was adopted. 5 mL of n-hexane ^{31,32} was added as extraction solvent and 1 g
8
9
209 of NaCl was added to induce the "salting out" phenomenon of the analytes, to facilitate the process.
10
11
210 After vortexing for 1 minute, the sample was set aside to await proper phase separation. Once the
13
14
211 correct separation between the aqueous and organic layers was achieved, 200 μL of the supernatant
15
16
212 were collected and transferred into a 250 μL vial containing activated anhydrous sodium sulfate, to
18
19
213 completely dehydrate the sample.
20
21
22
23
24

215 **2.4 Metagenomic DNA Extraction**

26

27
216 For each soil sample and each enrichment-derived bacterial consortia, three replicates were analyzed,
28
29
217 for a total of 93 soil samples and 27 enrichment samples. Soil samples were manually homogenized,
31
32
218 and 500 mg aliquots were collected. For bacterial consortia samples obtained from liquid cultures,
33
34
219 100 mg of cell pellet were collected. The cell pellet was obtained by serial centrifugation at $14,000 \times$
36
37
220 g for 5 min until the entire 5 mL sample had been processed. Genomic DNA of soil and cell pellet
38
39
221 samples was extracted using the FastDNATM SPIN Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals) and the FastPrep
41
42
222 Instrument (MP Biomedicals), following the manufacturer's instructions. DNA integrity was
43
44
223 evaluated by electrophoresis on a 1% agarose gel. DNA quantity was measured with a Qubit[®] 3.0
46
47
224 fluorometer (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions.
48
49
225 Sample purity was assessed by the 260/280 nm and 260/230 nm absorbance ratios.
50

226 51 227 **2.5 16S rDNA metabarcoding**

53
54
55

56
228 Illumina sequencing libraries were prepared by Novogene (Novogene Company Limited, Rm. 19C,
58
59
229 Lockhart Ctr., 301–307 Lockhart Rd., Wan Chai, Hong Kong). Bacteria were identified by specific
60
61
62
63
64
65

230 amplification of the V4–V5 hypervariable regions of the 16S rRNA gene using the forward primer
1
231 515F (5'-GTGCCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA-3') and the reverse primer 907R (5'-
3
232 CCGTCAATTCCTTTGAGTTT-3'). For both soil and cell-pellet samples, a total of 200 ng DNA was
4
5
6
233 used to generate the metagenomic libraries. Samples were sequenced in triplicate on an Illumina
7
8
9
234 NovaSeq 6000 platform with 250 bp paired end reads.
10

235 236 **2.6 Bioinformatic analysis**

237 Paired-end 250 bp reads from 16S libraries were demultiplexed by sample-specific barcodes and
18
238 trimmed with Cutadapt v4.6³³. Forward and reverse reads were merged, filtered (minimum Phred \geq
19
20
21
239 10), and screened for chimeras. Amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) were inferred using DADA2
22
23
240 v1.26 within QIIME2 v2023.2^{34–36}. Taxonomy was assigned with RESCRIPt v2023.2.0 in QIIME2
24
25
26
241³⁷, using a classifier trained on the corresponding hypervariable region from the SILVA 138 99% 16S
27
28
242 reference database. ASV tables were normalized by coverage-based standardization ($0.9950 \pm$
29
30
31
243 0.0025) implemented with iNEXT v3.0.2.³⁸ α -Diversity was quantified using the Hill–Simpson and
32
33
244 Hill–Shannon indices and the Chao1 richness estimator (metagMisc_R v0.5.0)^{39–41}. Statistical
34
35
245 significance was evaluated by Kruskal–Wallis test by ranks followed by Dunn’s post-hoc tests
36
37
38
246 (nparLD v2.2, rstatix v0.7.2)²⁸. Rarefaction curves of observed species were generated at the
39
40
247 specified coverage threshold.
41
42

248 The core microbiome for each microbial community was inferred from the complete ASV dataset
43
44
45
249 through a parameterised filtering workflows with specific stringency, aligned to the specific analytical
46
47
48
250 objective. Analyses were conceived as exploratory and hypothesis generating, relying on ASV based
49
50
251 taxonomic assignments to inform downstream functional interpretation rather than direct functional
51
52
252 inference from marker gene data. All statistical analyses were performed in R (v4.3.1) via RStudio
53
54
55
253 and Python (v3.12.3) via Pandas (v2.3.3) Bio.SeqIO (v1.85). For community composition analyses
56
57
254 (diversity and abundance metrics), we applied a high-stringency criterion that retained only ASVs
58
59
255 meeting both of the following requirements: (i) a prevalence $\geq 50\%$ (detected in at least half of the
60
61
62
63
64
65

256 biological triplicates) and (ii) a minimum detection threshold of 0.1% relative abundance. ASVs
1
257 falling below this limit were classified as ultra-low-frequency taxa and excluded due to their limited
3
258 representativeness of the core microbiome (microbiome v1.24.0). Shared taxa across samples were
4
5
6
259 visualized with flower plots generated using the EVenn online tool, which summarizes set
8
9
260 relationships ⁴². Differential abundances between soil-derived bacterial communities and enriched
10
11
261 bacterial consortia were assessed with ANCOM-BC2 (ANCOMBC v3.18). A less stringent filtering
13
14
262 scheme was implemented to assess the functional potential of the microbial ecology of the soil
15
16
263 samples and of the bacterial consortia. This approach employed a relative abundance threshold of
18
19
264 $\geq 0.2\%$ ^{43,44} and required ASVs to be present in at least 20% ⁴⁵ of the samples, ensuring the retention
20
21
265 of functionally relevant but potentially less dominant taxa. The filtered ASVs were compared against
22
23
266 the NCBI nucleotide database⁴⁶ using the BLASTn algorithm ⁴⁷ to infer potential genome-level
25
26
267 affiliations. To explore potential functional traits related to pollutant degradation, exploration of
27
28
268 functional traits related to pollutant degradation was therefore grounded on taxonomic affiliations
30
31
269 inferred from 16S rDNA ASVs and their association with the proteomic sequences of the candidate
32
33
270 genomes, instead of the detection of functional genes, providing putative, overall community-level
35
36
271 assessment of the contribution of each consortium to HCH degradation at each site. The strength of
37
38
272 this approach was that the retrieved protein datasets associated with each candidate genome were
40
41
273 aligned against a curated subset of the BIOSYSMOdb v1.0²⁶ specifically focused on lindane
42
43
274 degradation pathways in combination with UniProt specific annotation entries (available in
45
46
275 Supplementary Information) ^{26,48,49}. BLASTp searches were conducted using predefined similarity
47
48
276 thresholds selected to balance sensitivity and specificity in a screening-oriented context (minimum)
49
50
277 identity of 60%, e-value $\leq 1e-5$, and minimum query coverage of 80%) applied uniformly across all
52
53
278 samples to ensure methodological consistency across the different sites. Although, the identified *lin*
54
55
279 gene potential homologues were therefore considered putative, they are indicative of potential
57
58
280 functional affiliation, which in future studies will be tested further for evidence of confirmed
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

281 enzymatic activity or pathway completeness. The rationale and parameterisation of the filtering
1
282 workflows is described in detail in the Supplementary Information (SF1 and SF2)
2
3

283
4
5

284 3. Results 6 7 8

285 3.1 Soil sample chemical characterization 9 10

286 The HCH contamination levels in the soil samples collected at the three sites are presented in Table
11
12
13
14
287 1. The data were the results of Agrolab lab's quantification (Agrolab group, Italia). Soils from
15
16
288 Bitterfeld (Germany, DE) show uniformly quite elevated α -HCH.; notably, DE_BIT_03_A_S,
17
18
289 DE_BIT_04_A_S, DE_BIT_08_A_S, and DE_BIT_10_A_S contain 2000, 7500, 204, and 310 $mg \cdot$
19
20
290 kg^{-1} , respectively. β -HCH is likewise elevated in several DE samples—DE_BIT_04_A_S (135 $mg \cdot$
21
22
291 kg^{-1}), DE_BIT_10_A_S (93 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), DE_BIT_03_A_S (77 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), and
23
24
292 DE_BIT_08_A_S (74 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$).
25
26
27

293 These four are the most contaminated German soils, also exhibiting the highest δ - and γ -HCH values
28
29
30
31
294 (DE_BIT_04_A_S: 110 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ δ -HCH; 109 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ γ -HCH).
32
33

295 By contrast, soils from Colleferro (Italy, IT) display lower total HCH contamination. The α -HCH is
34
35
296 comparatively high in IT_COL_02_B_S (58.7 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), IT_COL_04_B_S (45 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), and
36
37
297 IT_COL_08_B_S (23.4 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$). The β -HCH peaks at 305 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ in IT_COL_04_B_S,
38
39
298 which is also among the highest total HCH concentrations (Σ -HCH = 355.3 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$). The highest
40
41
299 δ -HCH among Italian samples occurs in IT_COL_07_B_S (10 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), while γ -HCH reaches
42
43
300 8.5 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ in IT_COL_10_A_S. In Sabiñánigo (Spain, SP), contamination levels vary widely.
44
45
301 The most contaminated sample, SP_SAR_02_A_SL, contains 1 750 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ α -HCH, 85 $mg \cdot$
46
47
302 kg^{-1} β -HCH, 3 700 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ γ -HCH, and 2 090 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ δ -HCH, yielding a total of 7 625 $mg \cdot$
48
49
303 kg^{-1} Σ -HCH. Other Spanish samples show much lower levels: for instance, SP_SAR_03_A_S has
50
51
304 4.5 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ α -HCH, 26 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ β -HCH, 0.48 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ γ -HCH, and 0.77 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ δ -
52
53
305 HCH (Σ = 31.8 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$); while SP_INQ_01_A_S records 0.2 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ α -HCH, 2.45 $mg \cdot$
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

306 kg^{-1} β -HCH, 0.027 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ γ -HCH, and 0.078 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ δ -HCH ($\Sigma = 2.76 mg \cdot kg^{-1}$). Across
1
307 all soils, maximum α -HCH occurs in DE_BIT_04_A_S (7 500 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), The β -HCH peaks in
3
4
308 IT_COL_04_B_S (305 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$), and δ -/ γ -HCH attain their maxima in SP_SAR_02_A_SL (2 090
6
309 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ δ -HCH; 3 700 $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$ γ -HCH).
7
8
9

310

311 3.2 Enrichment of HCH degrading bacterial consortia from the three contaminated sites 13

312 The enriched bacterial consortia kinetics of HCH depletion were determined during their enrichment
14
16
313 process to distinguish the bacterial consortia on the base of their efficiency in the depletion of all the
18
19
314 different HCH isomers (Figure 1). HCH isomer concentrations were quantified at the setup of the
20
21
315 experimentation (day 0) and after 30 and 60 days of incubation. Figure 1, panel A shows the HCH
23
316 isomers concentrations over time of incubation for Bitterfeld bacterial consortia (Germany, DE). Any
25
26
317 bacterial consortia reduced α -, δ -, or γ -HCH concentrations to below 10 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ by day 60, whereas
28
29
318 several achieved levels as low as 5 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ for β -HCH. The most effective bacterial consortia were
30
31
319 DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002, DE_BIT_08_A_S_EC002, and DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002, which also
33
34
320 performed better than others across the other isomers. Notably, DE_BIT_08_A_S_EC002 showed the
35
36
321 lowest residual α -HCH concentration (16.49 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$) by day 60, followed by
38
39
322 DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002 (18.83 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$) and DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002 (17.98 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$). For β -
40
41
323 HCH, the same consortia exhibited final concentrations of 11.99, 14.61, and 8.66 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$,
43
44
324 respectively. Residual γ -HCH concentrations were 18.94 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ for DE_BIT_08_A_S_EC002,
45
46
325 20.43 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ for DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002, and 19.45 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ for DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002,
48
49
326 while δ -HCH remained at 18.25, 18.72, and 17.93 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$, respectively. Overall, the total HCH
50
51
327 residuals at day 60 were 65.69, 72.58, and 63.90 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$.
53

328 Figure 1, panel B summarizes HCH depletion by bacterial consortia enriched from Sabiñánigo soils
55
56
329 (Spain, SP). Depletion patterns varied across consortia. The most efficient were
58
330 SP_BA_01_A_S_EC002, SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002, SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002,
60
61
62
63
64
65

331 SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002, and SP_SAR_03_A_SL_EC002. By day 60, these exhibited the lowest
1
332 residual concentrations for α -HCH (ranging from 0.08 to 0.47 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$) and γ -HCH (0.32 to 0.37
3
333 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$). For δ -HCH, SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002, SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002, and
6
334 SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002 reached values close to 0 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ (complete depletion within
8
335 measurement error), while SP_SAR_03_A_SL_EC002 remained at 0.72 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ and
9
336 SP_BA_01_A_S_EC002 at 4.84 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$. The β -HCH residual concentrations ranged between 4.27
13
337 and 13.66 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$, with the lowest levels again in SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002 and
16
338 SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002. Three consortia, the—SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002,
18
339 SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002, and SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002—displayed mean total HCH residuals <
21
340 8 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ after 60 days.

24
341 Figure 1, panel C shows HCH isomer depletion by bacterial consortia isolated from Colleferro soils
26
342 (Italy, IT). All Colleferro consortia displayed similar degradation patterns, with almost complete
28
343 removal of α -, γ -, and δ -HCH. Residual α -HCH concentrations ranged from 0.26 to 0.69 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$
31
344 (average 0.41 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$), γ -HCH from 0.44 to 1.21 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ (average 0.77 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$), and δ -HCH
33
345 from 0.52 to 1.47 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ (average 1.04 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$). β -HCH showed higher persistence, with
36
346 residual values between 3.36 and 8.01 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$ (average 5.23 $mg \cdot L^{-1}$). The identified metabolites,
38
347 in all the microbial consortia analyzed, were γ -pentachlorocyclohexene (Table S2, panel A),
41
348 belonging the *lin* pathway. The intermediates of degradation δ -3,4,5,6-tetrachlorocyclohexene (Table
43
349 S2, panel B) and 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene (Table S2, panel C), not belonging to the *lin* pathway, were
46
350 also identified in all the microbial consortia analyzed. The reported intermediates were not detected
48
351 in the control extracts.

352 353 354 **3.3 Functional inference of the *lin* pathway of the three site soil samples and derived bacterial** 58 355 **consortia**

356 To assess a putative site-specific presence of the *lin* pathway as harboured by the bacterial
1
357 communities of the soil samples and its stability during the enrichment process of the different
3
358 bacterial consortia, metagenome-resolved inference was performed at the ASV level following the
4
5
6
359 filtering criteria described in Supplementary materials (SF1) providing an indirect, community-level
8
9
360 view of *lin*-associated functional potential. The inference aimed to minimize stochastic noise and
10
11
361 retain ecologically stable variants for downstream functional profiling related to the identification of
13
14
362 taxa potentially harbouring *lin* genes. The resulting datasets, as well as detailed counts of retained
15
16
363 ASVs, candidate genomes, and protein sequences for each country, are reported in the Supplementary
18
19
364 materials (SF2). From the German soil samples with no enrichment conditions, four ASVs were
20
21
365 associated with ten candidates' genomes containing *lin* gene homologues, yielding eighteen protein
23
24
366 hits assigned to LinB (haloalkane dehalogenase) and LinC (2,5-DDOL dehydrogenase). These ASVs
25
26
367 were associated to *Mycobacterium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Kribella*, *Streptomyces* spp. The recovered
27
28
368 enzymes correspond to the upper and intermediate modules of the *lin* pathway and collectively
30
31
369 support hydrolytic and oxidative degradation potential. No hits were detected for the lower pathway
32
33
370 enzymes (*LinD–LinF*), suggesting incomplete catabolic capacity by the *lin* pathway at the community
35
36
371 level. Under enrichment conditions, only three bacterial consortia the
37
38
372 DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002_T02, DE_BIT_08_A_S_EC002_T02 and DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002_T02
40
41
373 were associated with only one candidate genome, belonging to *Bradyrhizobium* sp., encoding only
42
43
374 LinB hits, indicating a functional contraction during the enrichment process and the loss of oxidative
45
46
375 capacity associated with LinC. In the Italian soils, three ASVs were linked to four candidate genomes.
47
48
376 The taxonomical characterisation indicated *Variovorax*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Methylorubrum*, *Geothrix*
49
50
377 spp. encoding for *linB* homologous genes, with no other *lin* genes detected. This configuration
52
53
378 restricts the soil activity to the initial hydrolytic dehalogenation step of the pathway. All the enriched
54
55
379 bacterial consortia showed a similar pattern, where four ASVs, belonging to *Variovorax*,
57
58
380 *Methylorubrum*, *Geothrix* and *Bradyrhizobium* genera, produced six candidate genomes and six *linB*
59
60
381 hit, suggesting the conservation of the encoding sequence for *linB* during the enrichment process.
62
63
64
65

382 Spanish soils yielded five candidate genomes associated with three ASV taxonomically affiliated with
1
383 *Sphingobium* sp., *Bradyrhizobium* sp. and *Kribbella* sp.. These candidate genomes collectively
3
384 encode twenty-five protein hits, spanning multiple gene families, including LinA, LinB, LinC, and
4
6
385 LinF. In contrast to the German and Italian this configuration spans all major functional modules of
8
386 the HCH degradation pathway from the initial dehydrochlorination (*linA*) through the hydrolytic and
9
10
387 dehydrogenative steps (*linB–C*), to the final ring-cleavage (*linF*). Notably the same pattern was
11
13
388 retained in the enriched bacterial consortia, suggesting potential conservation of the *lin* pathway
14
15
389 during the enrichment process, rather than a contraction toward partial pathway components. Overall,
16
18
390 these patterns point to distinct site specific configurations of *lin*-related functional potential across
20
21
391 regions, which are interpreted as indicative architectures at the bacterial taxonomical distribution
22
23
392 scale rather than strain-resolved complete pathways association.
25

393

394 **3.3 Microbial ecology of soils and derived HCH depleting bacterial consortia**

395 To tentatively depict the bacterial taxa responsible for the observed kinetics of HCH depletion, not
33
396 necessarily restricted to the presence of the intact *lin* pathway, three better performing bacterial
34
35
397 consortia for site were selected for better characterisation by downstream analysis. For the Italian site,
36
38
398 all consortia showed high degradation performance thus to ensure site representativeness,
39
40
399 IT_COL_03_C_S_EC002_T02, IT_COL_04_B_S_EC002_T02, and
41
43
400 IT_COL_10_A_S_EC002_T02 were selected, as they originated from distinct sampling areas. For
44
45
401 the Spanish site, the chosen consortia were SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002, SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002,
46
48
402 and SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002. For the German site the DE_BIT_09_A_S, DE_BIT_05_A_S and
50
51
403 DE_BIT_05_A_S.
52

404 Figure 2 shows the α -diversity profiles of the selected bacterial consortia. Based on Chao1 richness,
55
56
405 the German (DE) and Spanish (SP) bacterial consortia exhibit higher richness than those from
57
58
406 Colleferro (IT). An exception is SP_SAR_02_A_SL, which departs from the Spanish trend and
60
61
62
63
64
65

resembles the Italian ones. Hill–Simpson evenness indicates that Italian bacterial consortia are less even, except IT_COL_10_A_S, whose evenness is comparable to SP_BA_05_A_SL. Within the Spanish bacterial consortia, SP_SAR_02_A_SL also shows low evenness, whereas the German bacterial consortia are more heterogeneous, with DE_BIT_05_A_S exhibiting the highest evenness. Consistent with these patterns, the Hill–Shannon index, which integrates richness and evenness, shows that the Italian bacterial consortia are, on average, less diverse and less evenly distributed than those from German and Spanish one.

Comparing the three soil α -diversity with that of the deriving bacterial consortia for each region it is evident that the selective growth conditions during enrichment markedly shaped the bacterial consortia ecology (Figure 3). For the German site (Figure 3, Panel A) the selected consortia, DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002_T02, DE_BIT_04_A_S_EC002_T02, and DE_BIT_08_A_S_EC002_T02, display Chao1 values far below the soil averages one, indicating reduced richness. The strong selective pressure of the enrichment procedure narrowed the taxonomic breadth, lowering diversity. Evenness likewise dropped substantially, a trend corroborated by the Hill–Shannon index. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in all indices between selected bacterial consortia and soils, whereas diversity among the soil themselves did not differ significantly. Notably, soil Chao1 values are up to three orders of magnitude higher than those of the bacterial consortia (near zero). In relation to evenness, the Hill–Simpson declines from values on the order of hundreds in soils to near zero in bacterial consortia. Overall, enrichment led to a pronounced decrease in both richness and evenness relative to the source soils.

For the Spanish site (Figure 3, Panel B) the selected consortia exhibit marked reductions in both richness and evenness. Index values for the selected consortia approach zero, whereas the soils show Chao1 \sim 2,000 and Hill–Simpson on the order of hundreds. The contrast is less pronounced for SP_SAR_02_A_S relative to its corresponding consortium. The strongest statistical differences concern evenness (Hill–Simpson), underscoring a clear separation between soils and selected consortia, particularly for evenness. These results indicate that selective growth conditions altered

433 community ecology, reducing richness and especially evenness in the selected bacterial consortia
1
434 compared to the originating soils.
3
435 For the Italian site (Figure 3, Panel C) bacterial consortia show reduced richness, though Chao1
4
6
436 remains broadly comparable to the soils. Evenness is also similar between soils and bacterial
8
9
437 consortia, with uniformly low Hill–Simpson values across samples. IT_COL_10_A_S showed the
10
11
438 highest richness and evenness, diverging most from its corresponding bacterial consortia
13
14
439 (IT_COL_10_A_S_EC002_T02). Significant differences were detected both between selected
15
16
440 consortia and soils and among soils themselves. As highlighted in Figure 3, the most relevant contrasts
18
19
441 arise among soils, rather than between each soil and its matched consortium, with the exception of
20
21
442 IT_COL_10_A_S for Hill–Simpson. Consistently across regions, the Hill–Shannon index
23
24
443 corroborates these patterns, showing a clear separation between environmental soil bacterial
25
26
444 communities and their post-enrichment counterparts at all three sites.
27
28

445 30 446 **3.4 Core-microbiome characterization and composition analysis of the selected bacterial** 32 33 447 **consortia**

448 The core microbiomes of the selected HCH degrading bacterial consortia per site (site-specific core
37
38
449 microbiomes) were determined and results are shown in Figure 5, Panel A-C and associated Table
40
41
450 S1. A flower plot was produced to visualize taxa shared by all bacterial consortia core microbiome,
42
43
451 represented by the number at the centre of the flower plot. Table S1 reports the identification of the
45
46
452 taxa constituting the core microbiome of each site-specific enriched microbial consortia core
47
48
453 microbiome. The bacterial consortia selected from Colleferro are characterized by the highest number
49
50
454 of core taxa, whereas those from Sabiñánigo contain the lowest. The Bitterfeld bacterial consortia
52
53
455 show an intermediate number of core taxa but few unique taxa.
54

55
456 To determine whether the core taxa of the site-specific bacterial consortia could be involved in HCH
57
58
457 degradation, an analytical approach was adopted to assess whether their abundance increased during
59
60
458 the enrichment of the degrading bacterial consortia, assuming that such an increase is associated with
61

459 a functional involvement of these taxa in the process of HCH depletion. The analytical approach was
1
460 the Analysis of Composition of Microbiomes with Bias Correction (ANCOM-BC2)⁴². This group-
2
3
461 wise comparison identifies taxa whose abundances differ significantly between two samples and
4
5
6
462 quantifies the magnitude of those differences. We compared the soil bacterial communities with
7
8
9
463 bacterial consortia derived from the corresponding enrichment cultures to determine which soil taxa
10
11
464 were retained during the enrichment phase and whether their relative abundances increased or
12
13
465 decreased during the process. ANCOM-BC2 provides a statistically robust assessment of differential
14
15
16
466 abundances for specific taxa. Taxa that increased significantly under selective growth conditions were
17
18
467 considered candidate taxonomic markers of HCH-degrading bacterial consortia, as they are present
19
20
21
468 in the soil and are subsequently favoured by the applied selective conditions. Pointing out that the
22
23
469 composite genus names *Burkholderia–Caballeronia–Paraburkholderia* and *Allorhizobium–*
24
25
470 *Neorhizobium–Pararhizobium–Rhizobium* follow the SILVA 138.2 classifier used in our analyses.,
26
27
28
471 results obtained from the analysis are shown in Figure 6. In Figure 6 panel A, the core taxa from
29
30
31
472 Bitterfeld bacterial consortia (DE) *Stenotrophomonas*, *Pseudomonas*, *Variovorax*, JG30-KF-CM45,
32
33
473 *Burkholderia–Caballeronia–Paraburkholderia*, *Bradyrhizobium* show statistical differences in
34
35
474 abundance. Genera *Stenotrophomonas* and *Pseudomonas* are significantly more abundant in the three
36
37
38
475 selected Bitterfeld bacterial consortia (DE), while the genus *Achromobacter* is more abundant in two
39
40
476 out of three consortia (DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002_T02 and DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002_T02) than in
41
42
43
477 the corresponding soils. The genera JG30-KF-CM45, *Burkholderia–Caballeronia–Paraburkholderia*,
44
45
478 and *Bradyrhizobium* are less represented in the selected bacterial consortia than in their soils of origin.
46
47
48
479 In Figure 6, panel C, ANCOM-BC2 results for Colleferro are shown. *Pseudomonas*, *Cupriavidus* and
49
50
480 *Pseudolabrys* sp. are all present in the bacterial consortia core microbiome of Colleferro. *Cupriavidus*
51
52
53
481 increases significantly in all three selected bacterial consortia, while *Pseudomonas* and *Pseudolabrys*
54
55
482 increases both in IT_COL_04_B_S_EC002_T02 and in IT _COL_10_A_S_EC002_T02 and
56
57
483 IT_COL_03_C_S_EC002_T02 respectively. *Nocardioides* sp. is significantly more abundant in
58
59
60
484 IT_COL_10_A_S_EC002_T02 and IT_COL_04_B_S_EC002_T02, whereas it shows the opposite
61
62
63
64
65

485 behaviour, being significantly less abundant in IT_COL_03_C_S_EC002_T02. In Figure 6 panel B,
1
486 analysis of the Sabiñánigo-derived bacterial consortia highlights taxa well known for HCH
3
487 degradation, namely *Sphingobium* and *Sphingomonas*, genera not found in soils from the other
4
6 countries. *Sphingomonas* is significantly more abundant only in SP_SAR_02_A_SL_EC002_T02,
8
488 accompanied by a decrease in *Sphingobium*, whereas *Sphingobium* increases in the selected bacterial
9
489 consortia SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002_T02 and SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002_T02. The family
10
11 Xanthomonadaceae is more abundant in enrichment-derived bacterial consortia than in source soils
12
490 across all analyzed samples. In summary, any taxa significantly increasing in relative abundance
13
14 during the bacterial consortia enrichment process are shared across all the HCH depleting bacterial
15
491 consortia. However, site-specific candidates can be identified: in Bitterfeld (DE), *Stenotrophomonas*,
16
17
492 *Pseudomonas*, and *Achromobacter* spp; in Colleferro (IT), *Pseudomonas*, *Pseudolabrys*, and
18
19
493 *Cupriavidus* spp.; in Sabiñánigo (SP), *Sphingobium*, *Sphingomonas*, and the family
20
21
494 Xanthomonadaceae.
22
23
495
24
25
496
26
27
497
28
29
30
31
498
32
33
34

499 4. Discussion

500 The decontamination of recalcitrant xenobiotics in environmental matrices poses several challenges.
38
501 In matrices such as soils, it is desirable to adopt bio-based processes that exploit the catabolic
39
40
502 capacities of indigenous microorganisms to degrade pollutants while preserving the biogeochemical
41
42
503 cycles and the biodiversity of the treated matrix. Bacteria have demonstrated the ability to degrade
43
44
504 recalcitrant organic compounds, enabling the development of detoxification strategies both in the
45
46
505 laboratory and at field scale. In the case of HCH contamination, given the coexistence of four toxic
47
48
506 isomers with different degrees of recalcitrance due to their structural features, it is reasonable to
49
50
507 assume that the metabolic capacity of a bacterial consortia exceeds that of single strains. It is therefore
51
52
508 crucial to isolate bacterial consortia with the metabolic traits of interest when designing bio-based
53
54
509 approaches for the treatment of contaminated soils.
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

510 In this work, we developed a protocol to isolate bacterial consortia capable of degrading HCH,
1
511 starting from historically contaminated soils collected from geographically distinct areas. The
3
512 enrichment protocol here adopted enabled the isolation of bacterial consortia competent to degrade,
4
6
513 even with different efficiency, all four HCH isomers from each region. This enrichment protocol
8
514 overcame also the recalcitrance of the most recalcitrant isomers, δ and β ⁵⁰. Access to these bacterial
9
10
515 consortia provided an opportunity to investigate the microbial ecology of both the enriched
11
13
516 communities and their source soils, with the aim of identifying taxonomic and possibly functional
14
15
517 markers associated with HCH degradation.
16
18
518 By analysing soils from distant geographical regions, we observed that differing physicochemical
19
20
519 conditions significantly influence microbial community composition and structure, as shown by α -
21
23
520 diversity analyses. Bacterial consortia from the Bitterfeld (DE) and Sabiñánigo (SP) regions displayed
24
25
521 comparable values for the Chao1, Hill–Simpson, and Hill–Shannon indices, whereas Colleferro (IT)
26
27
522 bacterial consortia were less diverse and less evenly distributed. Another key finding from comparing
28
30
523 soil and isolated bacterial consortia is the marked reduction in biodiversity observed in the Bitterfeld
31
32
524 (DE) and Sabiñánigo (SP) bacterial consortia relative to their source soils. This result, consistent with
33
35
525 the strong selective stress applied during bacterial consortia enrichment process, is confirmed by the
36
37
526 sharp decrease in the Hill–Shannon index, which drops from average values around 1,000 in
38
40
527 environmental bacterial consortia to values near zero in the selected consortia. In contrast, bacterial
41
42
528 consortia isolated from Colleferro (IT) did not show a decrease in biodiversity as pronounced as that
43
44
529 seen in their source soils, suggesting greater resilience of the isolated bacterial consortia to the
45
47
530 selective pressure exerted during the enrichment process. This may reflect a better adaptation of the
48
49
531 soil microbial ecology to environmental conditions dominated by HCH presence and other factors
50
52
532 that might have altered the microbial community’s response to HCH. Results obtained suggest that
53
54
533 the observed biodiversity values may therefore reflect environmental conditions (e.g.: soil lithology,
55
57
534 pH, water content) more than the selective pressure exerted by the contaminant. Moreover, when
58
59
535 considering HCH isomer depletion kinetics, isolated bacterial consortia do not necessarily reflect the
60
61

536 biodiversity of their source soils. Depletion kinetics were broadly comparable between Colleferro
1
537 (IT) and Sabiñánigo (SP) bacterial consortias, while Bitterfeld (DE) exhibited lower levels of
3
538 removal. Thus, biodiversity in historically contaminated environments might be a not a reliable
4
6
539 indicator of greater metabolic potential toward the contaminant. Indeed, Bitterfeld (DE) yielded the
8
9
540 least efficient degrading bacterial consortia; Sabiñánigo (SP) displayed uneven capacities, and
10
11
541 Colleferro (IT) produced the most efficient bacterial consortia for oxidative HCH degradation. A high
13
14
542 level of soil microbial biodiversity in the presence of such a toxic contaminant is not necessarily
15
16
543 expected at historically contaminated sites. But, even when present, it cannot automatically be linked
18
19
544 to enhanced degradative capacity, and results obtained more convincingly point to microbial
20
21
545 communities that are tolerant to contamination rather than resistant because they can degrade the
23
546 contaminant. Consequently, biodiversity descriptors for HCH-contaminated soils cannot be used as
25
26
547 indices of the matrix's intrinsic degradation efficiency. More in details, Colleferro (IT) bacterial
27
28
548 consortia achieved the highest overall removal of HCH isomers, consistent with good adaptation of
30
31
549 local communities to the contaminant, possibly due to prolonged historical exposure that favoured
32
33
550 the selection of degrading taxa. In contrast, Bitterfeld (DE) bacterial consortia, despite originating
35
36
551 from highly contaminated soils, showed lower removal percentages, suggesting lower selective
37
38
552 efficiency or a different ecological equilibrium. Sabiñánigo (SP) bacterial consortia behaved more
40
41
553 heterogeneously, with SP_SAR_02_SL_EC002, SP_INQ_A_S_EC002, and
42
43
554 SP_BA_05_A_SL_EC002 particularly efficient and others less efficient in HCH depletion. A
45
46
555 particularly noteworthy aspect concerns the recalcitrant β -HCH. In Bitterfeld (DE) bacterial
47
48
556 consortias, β -HCH showed greater degradation relative to the other isomers, whereas in Colleferro
49
50
557 (IT) and Sabiñánigo (SP), degradation was more efficient for the other isomers and β -HCH remained
52
53
558 the most recalcitrant. At the same time, the comparison between the biodiversity indexes related to
54
55
559 the source and the product of a microbial enrichment process, might be considered a proxy of the
57
58
560 resilience and stability of the key players in the degradation of the contamination of interest during
59
60
561 the enrichment process. Thus, the above mentioned key players might be good candidates for the bio-

562 based approach of bioaugmentation. To identify specific microbial taxonomic markers that might
1
563 potentially indicate the efficiency of HCH oxidation since associated to all the HCH degrading
2
3
4
564 bacterial consortia, even though deriving from different sites, taxa shared across all selected enriched
5
6
565 bacterial consortia have been identified. The identified one did not increase significantly in relative
7
8
9
566 abundance during the bacterial consortia enrichment process, suggesting possible lack of direct
10
11
567 competence for HCH depletion but possible involvement in co-metabolic processes. Possible
12
13
14
568 candidate marker taxa for HCH depletion were identified since increasing during the enrichment
15
16
569 process. The core microbiome analysis revealed a set of taxa shared across all enriched HCH-
17
18
570 depleting consortia, indicating the presence of recurring community members despite their different
19
20
21
571 site origins. However, core membership alone does not necessarily imply direct involvement in HCH
22
23
572 depletion. For this reason, we interpreted core taxa considering their enrichment trajectories. Core
24
25
573 taxa that were consistently detected across all bacterial consortia but did not significantly increase in
26
27
28
574 relative abundance during enrichment, are less likely to represent primary HCH transforming bacteria
29
30
31
575 under the applied selective conditions, i.e. high concentration of HCH in presence of less concentrated
32
33
576 co-metabolic source of growth. Their persistence may instead reflect indirect or supportive roles
34
35
36
577 within the community, such as co-metabolic interactions, cross-feeding on transformation by-
37
38
578 products, provision of essential metabolites or cofactors, maintenance of redox balance and
39
40
579 community stability, and/or detoxification of inhibitory intermediates. In this context, these taxa may
41
42
43
580 contribute to consortium functioning without being directly competent for HCH depletion.
44
45
581 Conversely, taxa that significantly increased during enrichment are expected to be selectively
46
47
48
582 favoured by the imposed conditions, i.e., the presence of HCH and the associated selective pressure.
49
50
583 An enrichment-driven increase suggests a closer functional association with HCH depletion, either
51
52
53
584 through direct participation in depletion pathways or through tightly coupled metabolic interactions
54
55
585 that facilitate the process and benefit from it. Therefore, taxa showing consistent increases during
56
57
586 enrichment were prioritized as candidate marker taxa associated with HCH depletion. Results
58
59
60
61 obtained showed that for Bitterfeld (DE), the candidate markers are the genera *Pseudomonas*,

588 *Stenotrophomonas*, and *Achromobacter* spp. *Stenotrophomonas* sp. has been extensively studied for
1
589 its metabolic versatility and its ability to adapt to diverse environmental conditions; several species
2
3
4
590 have been isolated from soils contaminated by various xenobiotics, including organophosphate
5
6
591 pesticides, DDT, PAHs, and HCH. *Achromobacter* sp. increased significantly in two Bitterfeld
7
8
592 bacterial consortia (DE_BIT_03_A_S_EC002 and DE_BIT_10_A_S_EC002), which did not display
9
10
593 particularly high overall degradation but were able to degrade β -HCH, the most recalcitrant isomer.
11
12
594 *Achromobacter* sp. has been associated with the degradation of haloaromatic compounds and PAHs,
13
14
595 and genes involved in the metabolism of styrene, aminobenzoate, and benzoate have been
15
16
596 described^{51,52}. *Pseudomonas* sp. is well known for degrading HCH isomers, and *lin* genes have been
17
18
19
20
597 sequenced in *Pseudomonas* spp., where they are associated with HCH isomer metabolism^{53,54}.
21
22
23
598 *Pseudomonas* was also present in the core bacterial consortia of Colleferro (IT) bacterial consortia,
24
25
599 although it was significantly more abundant in only two consortia. Other genera that may be
26
27
600 considered Colleferro (IT) markers include *Cupriavidus* sp., which was significantly more abundant
28
29
30
601 in all selected bacterial consortia. *Cupriavidus* sp. has been isolated from microbial consortia capable
31
32
33
602 of degrading all four HCH isomers, and members of the family Burkholderiaceae, to which it belongs,
34
35
603 have been reported as degraders of a wide range of xenobiotics^{55,56}. *Nocardioides* sp. was also
36
37
38
604 observed as a Colleferro (IT) marker. *Nocardioides* spp are widespread in nature and have been
39
40
605 isolated from sediments, soils, and aquatic environments and organisms; they can transform complex
41
42
606 compounds and organic wastes, including crude oil, and many strains play important roles in
43
44
45
607 bioremediation, degrading a variety of pollutants (alkanes, pyridine, phenols, phenanthrene, and
46
47
48
608 others). Some *Nocardioides* strains degrade herbicides, including *N. jensenii*, which can degrade
49
50
609 dinitro-o-cresol-based herbicides^{57,58}. *Pseudolabrys* sp. has not been described for HCH isomer
51
52
610 degradation nor characterized for *lin* genes, but it is involved in the degradation of chloroalkanes,
53
54
55
611 chloroalkenes, and benzoate; dehalogenase functions have been inferred in both *Cupriavidus* and
56
57
612 *Pseudolabrys*, suggesting potential activity on fluorotelomers (PFAS)⁵⁹.
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

613 Regarding possible taxonomic markers characteristic of Sabiñánigo (SP) bacterial consortia,
1
614 *Sphingobium* sp. was significantly more abundant in SP_BA_05_A_S_EC002 and
3
615 SP_INQ_01_A_S_EC002, while *Sphingomonas* sp. was significant only in
4
6
616 SP_SAR_02_A_S_EC002. No taxa were simultaneously significantly more abundant across all three
8
9
617 Sabiñánigo (SP) bacterial consortia and present in their shared core. Both *Sphingobium* and
10
11
618 *Sphingomonas* spp. are well known for degrading HCH isomers. Strains such as *S. indicum* B90 and
13
14
619 *S. japonicum* UT26 are archetypes for the *lin* gene pathway and the associated HCH degradation
15
16
620 route. As previously assessed, the *lin* pathway is considered specific to HCH degradation^{60,61}. To date,
18
19
621 *lin* genes for lindane degradation have been identified mainly in Sphingomonadaceae (*Sphingobium*,
20
21
622 *Sphingomonas*, *Sphingopyxis*, *Novosphingobium*). Some studies nonetheless suggest that these genes,
23
24
623 or analogous enzymatic activities, may occur in other taxonomic groups (e.g., Pseudomonadales),
25
26
624 although it is not always clear whether they use the same *lin* genes or alternative metabolic routes.
27
28
625 The observation that some consortia, e.g., Colleferro (IT) and a subset from Sabiñánigo (SP) reached
30
31
626 similar levels of HCH depletion despite significantly different compositions suggests the action of
32
33
627 degradation pathways arising from convergent adaptive mechanisms.
35
36
628 To our knowledge, degradative functions for HCH have not been framed in terms of the metabolic
37
38
629 complexity of whole bacterial consortia; most pathways and enzymatic capacities implicated in HCH
40
41
630 degradation have been characterized in single microorganisms, and little is known about the
42
43
631 molecular mechanisms operating in competent consortia. Many taxa that constitute the core bacterial
45
46
632 consortia of the degrading consortia are not strictly linked to HCH isomer degradation, even though
47
48
633 they are reported to degrade other pollutants, including halogenated compounds such as chloroalkanes
49
50
634 and chloroalkenes, often via haloacid dehalogenases. Because of their broad substrate recognition,
52
53
635 these enzymes have been proposed as degraders of fluorinated compounds as well. Conversely,
54
55
636 Sabiñánigo bacterial consortia show involvement of Sphingomonadaceae, which are absent in
57
58
637 Colleferro (IT) and Bitterfeld (DE). The convergent adaptive mechanisms mentioned above, leading
59
60
638 to similar degradation efficiencies in compositionally different bacterial consortia, may be explained
62
63
64
65

639 by horizontal transfer of *lin* genes, as reported particularly within Sphingomonadaceae. This
1
640 assumption, however, must be weighed against the observation that, in the bacterial consortia studied
3
641 here, highly efficient HCH-degrading consortia (e.g., from Colleferro) lack Sphingomonadaceae,
4
6
642 implying that additional, as yet undescribed, metabolic pathways may contribute to HCH degradation.
8
9
643 Consistent with this hypothesis, analyses guided by taxonomic assignments inferred from ASV data
10
11
644 revealed distinct regional configurations of *lin*-associated functional potential. German bacterial
13
14
645 consortia displayed an intermediate profile characterised by truncated *lin*-associated gene
15
16
646 complements, suggestive of a putative partial oxidation process. Italian bacterial consortia exhibited
18
19
647 a highly constrained *lin*-associated profile, restricted to LinB-related hydrolytic potential. Notably,
20
21
648 taxa found in taxonomic assignments inferred from ASV data were not identified as site-specific
23
649 candidates for HCH depletion in previous analyses, suggesting a decoupling between *lin* gene
25
26
650 presence potential and observed degradation performance. On the other hand, the Spanish bacterial
27
28
651 consortia potentially retained the complete *lin* pathway harboured by *Sphingobium* sp. Collectively,
30
31
652 these patterns suggest that the metabolic potential for HCH transformation is geographically
32
33
653 structured and reflects long-term adaptive responses to site-specific contamination histories but is not
35
36
654 restricted to the presence of the *lin* pathway at least as a whole. The discrepancy between the high
37
38
655 HCH degrading kinetics observed in the Italian and German consortia and the putative absence of
40
41
656 complete *lin* gene set in these communities, in contrast to the Spanish consortia, suggests the presence
42
43
657 of alternative or complementary catabolic routes. While the detection of the *lin* pathway remains the
45
46
658 best characterised standard for HCH degradation, our taxonomically informed, ASV-level analyses,
47
48
659 provides strong indirect evidence that these communities may rely on complex inter-species
49
50
660 metabolic handovers to achieve HCH depletion, or employ different metabolic routes. The major
52
53
661 adaptive strategy in microbes involves the activation of broad-specificity catabolic pathways that
54
55
662 metabolize chemically diverse substrates, including xenobiotics, each of which can serve as a
57
58
663 potential carbon source. The KEGG ko00361 (“Chlorocyclohexane and chlorobenzene degradation
59
60
664 pathway” <https://www.kegg.jp/pathway/map00361>), which also includes the *lin* genes, features

665 dehalogenases not directly involved in HCH isomer transformation. By dehalogenating contaminants,
1
666 the pathway channels metabolites into the tricarboxylic acid cycle or benzoate degradation. Thus,
2
3
667 broad substrate recognition by such dehalogenases may be among the mechanisms contributing to
4
5
6
668 HCH degradation, in addition to the *lin* pathway, which appears largely confined to
7
8
9
669 Sphingomonadaceae. In this context, synergistic or competitive interactions among taxa in
10
11
670 multispecies consortia can shape metabolic functions differently than in isolated microorganisms and
12
13
671 may even enhance them via broadly distributed mechanisms across genera. In the present case, the
14
15
16
672 synergy would relate to dehalogenation of chlorinated compounds.
17
18
673 Supporting this interpretation, candidate marker taxa for Bitterfeld (DE) include *Achromobacter* sp.,
19
20
21
674 associated with genes involved in the degradation of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) within
22
23
675 ko00361, and *Stenotrophomonas* sp., reported to carry genes for the initial steps of the
24
25
676 chlorocyclohexane and chlorobenzene pathway^{62,63}. For Colleferro, *Cupriavidus* sp. harbors genes
26
27
28
677 and enzyme sets associated with the degradation of mono- and dichlorinated compounds, including
29
30
31
678 “tfd” genes also present in the cyclochlorohexane/chlorobenzene pathway, and *Pseudolabrys* sp. has
32
33
679 been described as carrying genes for the early steps of cyclochlorohexane and chlorobenzene
34
35
680 degradation^{64,65}. Therefore, the bacterial genera that increase significantly during bacterial consortia
36
37
38
681 isolation relative to the source soils are not necessarily carriers of the *lin* pathway but may possess
39
40
682 enzyme repertoires capable of dehalogenating a broad range of chlorinated compounds, comprising
41
42
683 HCH. To reinforce this assumption the metabolites of degradation of the HCH was attempted for all
43
44
45
684 the microbial consortia analysed. The identification of the intermediates of degradation of HCH by
46
47
48
685 the enriched microbial consortia was attempted assuming the involvement of the sole HCH
49
50
686 degradation pathway described so far, the *lin* pathway, and the possible alternative routes described
51
52
53
687 in the KEGG reference pathway map00361, the Chlorocyclohexane and chlorobenzene degradation,
54
55
688 <https://www.kegg.jp/pathway/map00361>. The initial attack on HCH isomers pathway, by the *lin*
56
57
689 pathway, includes for γ -HCH, the γ -pentachlorocyclohexene, successively to 1,3,4,6-tetrachloro-1,4-
58
59
690 cyclohexadiene, followed by 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene and 1,4-dichlorobenzene, proceeding through
60
61

691 chlorobenzene to 2,5-dichlorohydroquinone, then to chlorohydroquinone, hydroquinone, and finally
1
692 to maleylacetate. In relation to β -HCH it is sequentially degraded to δ -3,4,5,6-
3
693 tetrachlorocyclohexene, successively to 5,6-dichloro-1,3-cyclohexadiene and downstream
4
694 intermediates of benzene and chlorobenzene. In the context of the present experimentation the search
5
8
695 for metabolites belonging to the *lin* pathway focused on chlorinated metabolites, which necessarily
9
10
696 derive from the degradation of hexachlorocyclohexane. The identification of γ -
11
13
697 pentachlorocyclohexene within the microbiota confirmed the inferred presence of the *linB* genes in
14
15
698 all the microbial consortia. On the other hand, the detection of 1,2,4- trichlorobenzene and δ -3,4,5,6-
16
18
699 tetrachlorocyclohexene, not described as intermediates of the *lin* pathway (KEGG pathway
19
20
700 map00361, <https://www.kegg.jp/pathway/map00361>), further indicate that the consortia undertake
21
22
701 alternative degradative pathways. In the near future, to deepen the analysis of the alternative routes
23
25
702 of HCH degradation in the different consortia, labeled HCH will be adopted in experimentation
26
27
28
703 tailored for each single candidate, since the corresponding pathways might be different in the different
29
30
704 consortia.
31
32

706 5. Conclusions

707 This study demonstrates that indigenous soil bacterial consortia from three historically contaminated
33
34
708 sites can be selectively enriched to achieve efficient degradation of all four HCH isomers, including
35
36
709 the highly recalcitrant δ - and β -HCH. Despite substantial differences in soil properties and native
37
38
710 microbial communities, the enrichment protocol consistently yielded competent degraders,
39
40
711 confirming its robustness across heterogeneous matrices. Any taxa was identifies as common
41
42
712 microbial marker for oxidative HCH degradation. Instead, site-specific taxa emerged: *Pseudomonas*,
43
44
713 *Stenotrophomonas*, and *Achromobacter* in Bitterfeld; *Cupriavidus*, *Nocardioides*, and *Pseudolabrys*
45
46
714 in Colleferro; and *Sphingobium* and *Sphingomonas* in Sabiñánigo. The absence of
47
48
715 Sphingomonadaceae in the most efficient consortia (Colleferro), together with the predominance of
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

716 truncated *lin*-associated gene complements in Bitterfeld and Colleferro, supports the interpretation
1
717 that effective HCH degradation is not necessarily dependent on a complete *lin* pathway and may be
3
718 facilitated by non-Sphingomonadaceae taxa. Functional inference further suggested geographically
4
6
719 distinct configurations of the *lin* pathway and a long-term adaptive responses to site-specific
8
9
720 contamination history. Taken together our data, captured as community-level signals inferred from
10
11
721 exploratory taxonomic–functional analysis, indicate that HCH degradation arises from a combination
13
14
722 of *lin*-dependent and broader *lin*-independent dehalogenation mechanisms. captured as community-
15
16
723 level signals inferred from exploratory taxonomic–functional analysis. In this context, considering
18
19
724 that functional inference and increases in relative abundance support selection and association with
20
21
725 HCH depletion but not necessarily prove direct catabolic competence, additional functional evidence
23
24
726 (e.g., detection/expression of degradation genes) would be collected in the near future, also to
25
26
727 tentatively depict the extent to which each taxa contributes to HCH degradation within a bacterial
27
28
728 community.
30

31
729

32
730

References

35

731

1. Breivik K, Pacyna JM, Münch J. Use of α -, β - and γ -hexachlorocyclohexane in Europe, 1970–1996. *Science of The Total Environment*. 1999;239(1-3):151-163. doi:10.1016/S0048-9697(99)00291-0

732

38
733

40

734

2. Vijgen J, Abhilash PC, Li YF, et al. Hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) as new Stockholm Convention POPs-a global perspective on the management of Lindane and its waste isomers. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2011;18(2):152-162. doi:10.1007/S11356-010-0417-9/TABLES/2

735

43
736

46

737

3. Nayyar N, Sangwan N, Kohli P, et al. Hexachlorocyclohexane: Persistence, toxicity and decontamination. *Rev Environ Health*. 2014;29(1-2):49-52. doi:10.1515/REVEH-2014-0015/XML

738

48
739

51

740

4. Li YF, Cai DJ, Singh A. Technical hexachlorocyclohexane use trends in China and their impact on the environment. *Arch Environ Contam Toxicol*. 1998;35(4):688-697. doi:10.1007/S002449900432/METRICS

741

53
742

56

743

5. Murthy HMR, Manonmani HK. Aerobic degradation of technical hexachlorocyclohexane by a defined microbial consortium. 2007;149(1):18-25. doi:10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2007.03.053

744

58
745

61

62

63

64

65

- 747
748
749
750
751
752
753
754
755
756
757
758
759
760
761
762
763
764
765
766
767
768
769
770
771
772
773
774
775
776
777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
6. Manonmani HK, Chandrashekaraiiah DH, Sreedhar Reddy N, Elcey CD, Kunhi AAM. Isolation and acclimation of a microbial consortium for improved aerobic degradation of α -hexachlorocyclohexane. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2000;48(9):4341-4351. doi:10.1021/JF990712C/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/JF990712CF00008.JPEG
 7. Nagata Y, Endo R, Ito M, Ohtsubo Y, Tsuda M. Aerobic degradation of lindane (gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane) in bacteria and its biochemical and molecular basis. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2007;76(4):741-752. doi:10.1007/S00253-007-1066-X
 8. Nagasawa S, Kikuchi R, Nagata Y, Takagi M, Matsuo M. Aerobic mineralization of γ -HCH by *Pseudomonas paucimobilis* UT26. *Chemosphere.* 1993;26(9):1719-1728. doi:10.1016/0045-6535(93)90115-L
 9. Sahu SK, Patnaik KK, Sharmila M, Sethunathan N. Degradation of Alpha-, Beta-, and Gamma-Hexachlorocyclohexane by a Soil Bacterium under Aerobic Conditions. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 1990;56(11):3620-3622. doi:10.1128/AEM.56.11.3620-3622.1990
 10. Hynková K, Nagata Y, Takagi M, Damborský J. Identification of the catalytic triad in the haloalkane dehalogenase from *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* UT26. *FEBS Lett.* 1999;446(1):177-181. doi:10.1016/S0014-5793(99)00199-4
 11. Nagata Y, Miyauchi K, Takagi M. Complete analysis of genes and enzymes for γ -hexachlorocyclohexane degradation in *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* UT26. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1999;23(4-5):380-390. doi:10.1038/SJ.JIM.2900736
 12. Nagata Y, Ohtsubo Y, Tsuda M. Properties and biotechnological applications of natural and engineered haloalkane dehalogenases. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2015;99(23):9865-9881. doi:10.1007/S00253-015-6954-X
 13. Nagata Y, Tabata M, Ohtsubo Y, Tsuda M. Biodegradation of Organochlorine Pesticides. *Manual of Environmental Microbiology.* Published online September 1, 2015;5.1.2-1-5.1.2-30. doi:10.1128/9781555818821.CH5.1.2
 14. Miyauchi K, Suh SK, Nagata Y, Takagi M. Cloning and sequencing of a 2,5-dichlorohydroquinone reductive dehalogenase gene whose product is involved in degradation of gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane by *Sphingomonas paucimobilis*. *J Bacteriol.* 1998;180(6):1354-1359. doi:10.1128/JB.180.6.1354-1359.1998
 15. Endo R, Ohtsubo Y, Tsuda M, Nagata Y. Growth inhibition by metabolites of gamma-hexachlorocyclohexane in *Sphingobium japonicum* UT26. *Biosci Biotechnol Biochem.* 2006;70(4):1029-1032. doi:10.1271/BBB.70.1029
 16. Verma H, Kumar R, Oldach P, et al. Comparative genomic analysis of nine *Sphingobium* strains: Insights into their evolution and hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH) degradation pathways. *BMC Genomics.* 2014;15(1). doi:10.1186/1471-2164-15-1014/
 17. Pal R, Bala S, Dadhwal M, et al. Hexachlorocyclohexane-degrading bacterial strains *Sphingomonas paucimobilis* B90A. UT26 and Sp⁺, having similar lin genes, represent three distinct species, *Sphingobium indicum* sp. nov., *Sphingobium japonicum* sp. nov.

- 785 and *Sphingobium francense* sp. nov., and reclassification of [*Sphingomonas*]
786 *chungbukensis* as *Sphingobium chungbukense* comb. nov. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol.*
787 2005;55(5):1965-1972. doi:10.1099/IJS.0.63201-0
- 788 18. Jariyal M, Jindal V, Mandal K, Gupta VK, Singh B. Bioremediation of
789 organophosphorus pesticide phorate in soil by microbial consortia. *Ecotoxicol Environ*
790 *Saf.* 2018;159:310-316. doi:10.1016/J.ECOENV.2018.04.063
- 791 19. Lal D, Jindal S, Kumari H, et al. Bacterial diversity and real-time PCR based
792 assessment of *linA* and *linB* gene distribution at hexachlorocyclohexane contaminated
793 sites. *J Basic Microbiol.* 2015;55(3):363-373. doi:10.1002/JOBM.201300211
- 794 20. Manickam N, Mau M, Schlömann M. Characterization of the novel HCH-degrading
795 strain, *Microbacterium* sp. ITRC1. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2006;69(5):580-588.
796 doi:10.1007/S00253-005-0162-Z
- 797 21. Manickam N, Misra R, Mayilraj S. A novel pathway for the biodegradation of γ -
798 hexachlorocyclohexane by a *Xanthomonas* sp. strain ICH12. *J Appl Microbiol.*
799 2007;102(6):1468-1478. doi:10.1111/J.1365-2672.2006.03209.X
- 800 22. Manickam N, Reddy MK, Saini HS, Shanker R. Isolation of hexachlorocyclohexane-
801 degrading *Sphingomonas* sp. by dehalogenase assay and characterization of genes
802 involved in γ -HCH degradation. *J Appl Microbiol.* 2008;104(4):952-960.
803 doi:10.1111/J.1365-2672.2007.03610.X
- 804 23. Lal R, Dogra C, Malhotra S, Sharma P, Pal R. Diversity, distribution and divergence of
805 *lin* genes in hexachlorocyclohexane-degrading sphingomonads. *Trends Biotechnol.*
806 2006;24(3):121-130. doi:10.1016/J.TIBTECH.2006.01.005
- 807 24. Lal R, Dadhwal M, Kumari K, et al. *Pseudomonas* sp. to *Sphingobium indicum*: A
808 journey of microbial degradation and bioremediation of Hexachlorocyclohexane.
809 *Indian J Microbiol.* 2008;48(1):3-18. doi:10.1007/S12088-008-0002-9
- 810 25. Sangwan N, Lata P, Dwivedi V, et al. Comparative Metagenomic Analysis of Soil
811 Microbial Communities across Three Hexachlorocyclohexane Contamination Levels.
812 *PLoS One.* 2012;7(9):e46219. doi:10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0046219
- 813 26. Gil-Guerrero S, Division IDENERAB, Otero-Gonzalez L, Franco de Benito M, Hall
814 A. BIOSYSMOdb: Curated Database for Biodegradation and Bioremediation. *Zenodo.*
815 Published online February 2025. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.14795254
- 816 27. Bernabei G, De Simone G, Becarelli S, Di Mambro R, Gentini A, Di Gregorio S. Co-
817 metabolic growth and microbial diversity: Keys for the depletion of the α , δ , β and γ -
818 HCH isomers. *J Hazard Mater.* 2024 Dec 5;480:135963. doi:
819 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.135963.
- 820 28. Noguchi K, Gel YR, Brunner E, Konietzschke F. nparLD: An R Software Package for
821 the Nonparametric Analysis of Longitudinal Data in Factorial Experiments. *J Stat*
822 *Softw.* 2012;50(12):1-23. doi:10.18637/JSS.V050.I12

- 823 29. Portolés T, Pitarch E, López FJ, Sancho J V., Hernández F. Methodical approach for the use
824 of GC-TOF MS for screening and confirmation of organic pollutants in environmental water.
825 *Journal of Mass Spectrometry*. 2007;42(9):1175-1185. doi:10.1002/jms.1248
- 826 30. Lesueur C, Gartner M, Mentler A, Fuerhacker M. Comparison of four extraction methods for
827 the analysis of 24 pesticides in soil samples with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry
828 and liquid chromatography–ion trap–mass spectrometry. *Talanta*. 2008;75(1):284-293.
829 doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2007.11.031
- 830 31. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. *Method 8081B: Organochlorine Pesticides by Gas*
831 *Chromatography*. 2007. [https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-](https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-12/documents/8081b.pdf)
832 [12/documents/8081b.pdf](https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-12/documents/8081b.pdf)
- 833 32. Khan MI, Yoo K, Schwab L, Kümmel S, Nijenhuis I. Characterization of anaerobic
834 biotransformation of hexachlorocyclohexanes by novel microbial consortia enriched from
835 channel and river sediments. *J Hazard Mater*. 2024;476(2):135198.
836 doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2024.135198
- 837 33. Martin M. Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads.
838 *EMBnet J*. 2011;17(1):10-12. doi:10.14806/EJ.17.1.200
- 839 34. Nearing JT, Douglas GM, Comeau AM, Langille MGI. Denoising the Denoisers: an
840 independent evaluation of microbiome sequence error-correction approaches. *PeerJ*.
841 2018;6(8):e5364. doi:10.7717/peerj.5364
- 842 35. Prodan A, Tremaroli V, Brolin H, Zwinderman AH, Nieuwdorp M, Levin E. Comparing
843 bioinformatic pipelines for microbial 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing. *PLoS One*.
844 2020;15(1):e0227434. doi:10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0227434
- 845 36. Bolyen E, Rideout JR, Dillon MR, et al. Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible
846 microbiome data science using QIIME 2. *Nat Biotechnol*. 2019;37(8):852-857.
847 doi:10.1038/s41587-019-0209-9
- 848 37. Robeson MS, O'Rourke DR, Kaehler BD, et al. RESCRIPt: Reproducible sequence
849 taxonomy reference database management. *PLoS Comput Biol*. 2021;17(11):e1009581.
850 doi:10.1371/JOURNAL.PCBI.1009581
- 851 38. Hsieh TC, Ma KH, Chao A. iNEXT: an R package for rarefaction and extrapolation of
852 species diversity (Hill numbers). *Methods Ecol Evol*. 2016;7(12):1451-1456.
853 doi:10.1111/2041-210X.12613
- 854 39. Chao A, Gotelli NJ, Hsieh TC, et al. Rarefaction and extrapolation with Hill numbers: A
855 framework for sampling and estimation in species diversity studies. *Ecol Monogr*.
856 2014;84(1):45-67. doi:10.1890/13-0133.1
- 857 40. Alberdi A, Gilbert MTP. A guide to the application of Hill numbers to DNA-based diversity
858 analyses. *Mol Ecol Resour*. 2019;19(4):804-817. doi:10.1111/1755-0998.13014

- 859 41. Gotelli NJ, Chao A. Measuring and Estimating Species Richness, Species Diversity, and
860 Biotic Similarity from Sampling Data. In: *Encyclopedia of Biodiversity: Second Edition*.
861 2013. doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-384719-5.00424-X
- 862 42. Lin H, Peddada S Das. Multigroup analysis of compositions of microbiomes with covariate
863 adjustments and repeated measures. *Nature Methods* 2023 21:1. 2023;21(1):83-91.
864 doi:10.1038/s41592-023-02092-7
- 865 43. Edwin NR, Fitzpatrick AH, Brennan F, Abram F, O’Sullivan O. An in-depth evaluation of
866 metagenomic classifiers for soil microbiomes. *Environ Microbiome*. 2024;19(1):19.
867 doi:10.1186/S40793-024-00561-W
- 868 44. Reitmeier S, Hitch TCA, Treichel N, et al. Handling of spurious sequences affects the
869 outcome of high-throughput 16S rRNA gene amplicon profiling. *ISME Communications*.
870 2021;1(1):31. doi:10.1038/S43705-021-00033-Z
- 871 45. Chen H, Ma K, Lu C, et al. Functional Redundancy in Soil Microbial Community Based on
872 Metagenomics Across the Globe. *Front Microbiol*. 2022;13:878978.
873 doi:10.3389/FMICB.2022.878978/BIBTEX
- 874 46. Sayers EW, Bolton EE, Brister JR, et al. Database resources of the national center for
875 biotechnology information. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2022;50(D1):D20-D26.
876 doi:10.1093/NAR/GKAB1112
- 877 47. Camacho C, Coulouris G, Avagyan V, et al. BLAST+: architecture and applications. *BMC*
878 *Bioinformatics* 2009 10:1. 2009;10(1):421-. doi:10.1186/1471-2105-10-421
- 879 48. Bateman A, Martin MJ, Orchard S, et al. UniProt: the Universal Protein Knowledgebase in
880 2023. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2023;51(D1):D523-D531. doi:10.1093/NAR/GKAC1052
- 881 49. Cock PJA, Antao T, Chang JT, et al. Biopython: freely available Python tools for
882 computational molecular biology and bioinformatics. *Bioinformatics*. 2009;25(11):1422-
883 1423. doi:10.1093/BIOINFORMATICS/BTP163
- 884 50. Willett KL, Ulrich EM, Hites RA, K Willett EURH. Differential toxicity and environmental
885 fates of hexachlorocyclohexane isomers. 1998;32(15):2197-2207. doi:10.1021/ES9708530
- 886 51. Marzec-Grządziel A, Gałazka A. Sequencing of the Whole Genome of a Bacterium of the
887 Genus *Achromobacter* Reveals Its Potential for Xenobiotics Biodegradation. *Agriculture*
888 2023, Vol 13, Page 1519. 2023;13(8):1519. doi:10.3390/AGRICULTURE13081519
- 889 52. Gao S, Seo JS, Wang J, Keum YS, Li J, Li QX. Multiple degradation pathways of
890 phenanthrene by *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* C6. *Int Biodeterior Biodegradation*.
891 2013;79:98-104. doi:10.1016/J.IBIOD.2013.01.012
- 892 53. Lodha B, Bhat P, Kumar MS, et al. Bioisomerization kinetics of γ -HCH and biokinetics of
893 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* degrading technical HCH. *Biochem Eng J*. 2007;35(1):12-19.
894 doi:10.1016/J.BEJ.2006.12.015

- 895 54. Singh AK, Chaudhary P, Macwan AS, Diwedi UN, Kumar A. Selective loss of lin genes from
896 hexachlorocyclohexane-degrading *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ITRC-5 under different growth
897 conditions. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2007;76(4):895-901. doi:10.1007/s00253-007-1056-z
898 55. Singh AK, Chaudhary P, Macwan AS, Diwedi UN, Kumar A. Selective loss of lin genes from
899 hexachlorocyclohexane-degrading *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ITRC-5 under different growth
900 conditions. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2007 76:4. 2007;76(4):895-901.
901 doi:10.1007/S00253-007-1056-Z
902 56. Srivastava V, Dhuliya S, Kumar MS. Biodegradation of technical hexachlorocyclohexane by
903 *Cupriavidus malaysiensis*. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2022 38:6.
904 2022;38(6):108-. doi:10.1007/S11274-022-03284-7
905 57. Zhu L, Yang B, Guo W, et al. *Nocardioides limicola* sp. nov., an alkaliphilic alkane
906 degrading bacterium isolated from oilfield alkali-saline soil. *Antonie van Leeuwenhoek* 2024
907 117:1. 2024;117(1):14-. doi:10.1007/S10482-023-01907-Z
908 58. Kumar D. Biodegradation of γ -Hexachlorocyclohexane by *Burkholderia* sp. IPL04. *Biocatal*
909 *Agric Biotechnol.* 2018;16:331-339. doi:10.1016/J.BCAB.2018.09.001
910 59. Manucharova NA, Bolshakova MA, Babich TL, et al. Microbial Degradation of Petroleum and
911 Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons from Sod-Podzolic Soil. *Microbiology* 2021 90:6.
912 2021;90(6):743-753. doi:10.1134/S0026261721060096
913 60. Zheng G, Selvam A, Wong JWC. Rapid degradation of lindane (γ -hexachlorocyclohexane) at
914 low temperature by *Sphingobium* strains. *Int Biodeterior Biodegradation.* 2011;65(4):612-
915 618. doi:10.1016/J.IBIOD.2011.03.005
916 61. Dong S, Yan PF, Mezzari MP, Abriola LM, Pennell KD, Cápiro NL. Using Network Analysis
917 and Predictive Functional Analysis to Explore the Fluorotelomer Biotransformation Potential
918 of Soil Microbial Communities. *Environ Sci Technol.* 2024;58(17):7480-7492.
919 doi:10.1021/ACS.EST.4C00942
920 62. Raina V, Mrutyunjay AE, Ae S, et al. Enhanced biodegradation of hexachlorocyclohexane
921 (HCH) in contaminated soils via inoculation with *Sphingobium indicum* B90A.
922 *Biodegradation* 2007 19:1. 2007;19(1):27-40. doi:10.1007/S10532-007-9112-Z
923 63. Vedler E, Vahter M, Heinaru A. The completely sequenced plasmid pEST4011 contains a
924 novel IncP1 backbone and a catabolic transposon harboring *tfd* genes for 2,4-
925 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid degradation. *J Bacteriol.* 2004;186(21):7161-7174.
926 doi:10.1128/JB.186.21.7161-
927 7174.2004;JOURNAL:JOURNAL:JB;WGROU:STRING:PUBLICATION
928 64. Pérez-Pantoja D, De La Iglesia R, Pieper DH, González B. Metabolic reconstruction of
929 aromatic compounds degradation from the genome of the amazing pollutant-degrading
930 bacterium *Cupriavidus necator* JMP134. *FEMS Microbiol Rev.* 2008;32(5):736-794.
931 doi:10.1111/J.1574-6976.2008.00122.X

932
933
934
935
936
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

65. Vera A, Wilson FP, Cupples AM. Predicted functional genes for the biodegradation of xenobiotics in groundwater and sediment at two contaminated naval sites. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2022 106:2. 2022;106(2):835-853. doi:10.1007/S00253-021-11756-3

Acknowledgments

This study was part of the EU-MIBIREM and EU-BIOSYSMO projects funded by the European Union (Grant agreements ID: 101059260 and 101060211).

Table1: The soils concentration of each HCH-isomers is reported as $mg \cdot kg^{-1}$. RSD (7-15%)

Country	Samples	α -HCH	β -HCH	γ -HCH	δ -HCH	Σ -HCH
Spain	SP_BA_01_A_S	0,0029	0,00191	0,0027	0,01	0,01751
Spain	SP_BA_02_A_S	0,073	0,084	0,077	0,085	0,319
Spain	SP_BA_03_A_S	0,146	0,0077	0,161	0,3	0,6147
Spain	SP_BA_04_A_S	0,0199	0,021	0,023	0,165	0,2289
Spain	SP_BA_05_A_SL	0,31	0,92	0,0159	0,034	1,2799
Spain	SP_INQ_01_A_S	0,2	2,45	0,027	0,078	2,755
Spain	SP_INQ_02_A_S	0,0098	0,3	0,0093	0,036	0,3551
Spain	SP_SAR_01_A_S	0,207	0,173	0,145	0,53	1,055
Spain	SP_SAR_02_A_SL	1750	85	3700	2090	7625
Spain	SP_SAR_03_A_S	4,5	26	0,48	0,77	31,75
Germany	DE_BIT_01_A_S	0,62	0,95	0,0084	0,01	1,5884
Germany	DE_BIT_02_A_S	1,43	2,5	0,0097	0,0117	3,9514
Germany	DE_BIT_03_A_S	2000	77	24,7	9,5	2111,2
Germany	DE_BIT_04_A_S	7500	135	109	110	7854
Germany	DE_BIT_05_A_S	0,167	0,19	0,001	0,01	0,368
Germany	DE_BIT_06_A_S	3,5	1,59	0,025	0,01	5,125
Germany	DE_BIT_07_A_S	0,92	1,08	0,0154	0,027	2,0424
Germany	DE_BIT_08_A_S	204	74	3,5	1,44	282,94
Germany	DE_BIT_09_A_S	13,9	41	0,144	0,239	55,283
Germany	DE_BIT_10_A_S	310	93	4	2,31	409,31
Italy	IT_COL_01_C_S	6,7	0,0617	0,452	0,01	7,2237
Italy	IT_COL_02_B_S	58,7	0,75	4,86	0,099	64,409
Italy	IT_COL_03_C_S	0,594	0,505	0,0612	0,83	1,9902
Italy	IT_COL_04_B_S	45	305	0,103	5,2	355,303
Italy	IT_COL_05_C_S	10,7	1,16	0,75	4,7	17,31
Italy	IT_COL_06_C_S	0,0014	0,0018	0,0019	0,01	0,0151
Italy	IT_COL_07_B_S	18,9	16,7	2,24	10	47,84
Italy	IT_COL_08_B_S	23,4	4,18	0,386	2,41	30,376
Italy	IT_COL_09_A_S	0,0259	0,0092	0,094	0,027	0,1561
Italy	IT_COL_10_A_S	0,067	0,132	8,5	1,25	9,949
Italy	IT_COL_11_C_S	0,0023	0,003	0,0031	0,01	0,0184
Italy	IT_COL_12_C_S	0,79	0,14	0,087	0,04	1,057

Figure 1. Boxplots of α -, β -, γ -, and δ -HCH isomer concentrations, and their sum, measured at the enrichment protocol time points. The figure reports data for selected samples from Bitterfeld (Panel A), Sabiñánigo (Panel B), and Colleferro (Panel C) at setup (Day 0), Day 30, and Day 60. Post hoc comparisons use Dunn's test with Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple testing. Asterisks above the boxplots denote statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between each sample and the control (Blank). All remaining pairwise comparisons are provided in the Supplementary Material for brevity and ease of interpretation (S3 for Germany, S4 for Italy and S5 for Spain).

Figure 2. α -diversity indexes of the soil samples of the tree country (Bitterfeld (DE), Colleferro (IT), Sabinánigo (SP)). Chao1 (A), Hill–Shannon (B), and Hill–Simpson (C) indices, each computed after coverage-based rarefaction at 98%, and rarefaction curves of observed species for the bacterial community (D). Boxplots show the minimum (Q0), first quartile (Q1), median (Q2), third quartile (Q3), and maximum (Q4) for each group. The reported p-value is from a Kruskal–Wallis test ($\alpha = 0.05$). Post hoc comparisons use Dunn’s test with Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple testing.

Figure 3. α -diversity metrics of soils from the three contaminated sites and the deriving microbiomes. Panel A – Bitterfeld (DE), Panel B – Sabiñánigo (SP), Panel C – Colleferro (IT). Chao1 index (i), Hill–Shannon (ii), and Hill–Simpson (iii), each computed after 98% coverage-based rarefaction, and rarefaction curves of observed species in the bacterial community composition (iv). Boxplots show the minimum (Q0), first quartile (Q1), median (Q2), third quartile (Q3), and maximum (Q4) for each group. The reported p-value is from a Kruskal–Wallis test ($\alpha = 0.05$). Post hoc statistics are based on Dunn’s test with Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons.

Your image file "Fig_3.png" cannot be opened and processed. Please see the common list of problems, and suggested resolutions below.

Reason: The image file is corrupt or invalid. Please check and resubmit.

Other Common Problems When Creating a PDF from an image file

You will need to convert your image file to another format or fix the current image, then re-submit it.

Figure 4

[Click here to access/download;Figure;Fig_4.png](#)

Figure 4 α -diversity metrics of selected microbiomes from Bitterfeld, Colleferro, and Sabinánigo. Chao1 index (A), Hill–Shannon (B), and Hill–Simpson (C), each computed after 98% coverage-based rarefaction, and rarefaction curves of observed species in the bacterial community composition (D). Boxplots show the minimum (Q0), first quartile (Q1), median (Q2), third quartile (Q3), and maximum (Q4) for each group. The reported p-value is from a Kruskal–Wallis test ($\alpha = 0.05$). Post hoc statistics are based on Dunn’s test with Benjamini–Hochberg correction for multiple comparisons.

Figure 5. Flower plot showing the intersection among the core microbiomes of microbiomes obtained by enrichment from Bitterfeld (A), Colleferro (B), and Sabiñánigo (C). The center indicates the number of taxa shared across all samples. The flower plot was generated with the EVen software ¹.

Fig. 6. Analysis of Composition of Microbiomes with Bias Correction (ANCOM-BC). On the horizontal axis are the log-transformed differential abundance values of each taxon between the two compared samples. Shown are comparisons between the environmental microbiomes and the corresponding selected microbiomes for Bitterfeld (Panel A), Colleferro (Panel B), and Sabiñánigo (Panel C).

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
Table S1.docx

[Click here to access/download](#)

Supplementary Material

SF1-Supplementary Information_Methodology.docx

[Click here to access/download](#)

Supplementary Material

SF2-Protein_coinc_HCHprot_vs_GenCandProt.xlsx

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
S3_DE.csv

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
S4_IT.csv

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
S5_SP.CSV

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
Table S2.docx

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.